

ECONOMIC CULTURE OF SCHOOLCHILDREN AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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Abstract. *Work experience shows that economic education at an early age helps children develop economic thinking, master the conceptual apparatus so necessary for orientation in the modern market world. The purpose of economic education will be the acquisition of elementary skills of behavior in market conditions, the creation of a conceptual basis for further, deeper study of economics in high school.*

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For supporters of the "personal" approach, culture is a personal aspect of human existence, the process of creative activity, the creation of the human world by man. Based on the interpretation of culture as a certain measure of the formation, development and realization of the essential forces of a person in his social activity, its role in the development of personality is also revealed.

Culture (Latin cultura) literally means "cultivation", "processing". For the first time it was introduced into scientific circulation by the ancient philosopher Cicero and implied the purposeful influence of man on nature, as well as the upbringing and education of man himself.

The concept of "culture" in the philosophical encyclopedic dictionary is interpreted as a specific way of organizing and developing human life, represented in the products of material and spiritual labor, in the system of social norms and institutions, in spiritual values, in the totality of people's relations to nature, among themselves and to themselves.

The main goals, objectives and principles of economic education of primary school students. Work experience shows that economic education at an early age helps children develop economic thinking, master the conceptual apparatus so necessary for orientation in the modern market world. The purpose of economic education will be the acquisition of elementary skills of behavior in market conditions, the creation of a conceptual basis for further, deeper study of economics in high school. The main tasks are:

- in the field of education – mastering the basics of knowledge about the modern economy, the principles and laws of its functioning, the skills of economic activity;

- in the sphere of self-awareness – comprehension of one's individual potential, formation of conscious civic economic behavior;

- in the field of motivation – the development of interest in the problems of the country's economy and family, the constant need for new knowledge, the desire for self-expression and self-realization, which should become a means of social protection, adaptation to market conditions.

The implementation of the set tasks and goals can go by:

Integration of economics with mathematics or technology, where economic knowledge will find a practical way out (mathematical calculations, personality qualities – diligence, entrepreneurship, economy).

We will be guided by the principles of developmental learning:

- the focus of learning on the development of the student's personality;
- the subjective position of the student in cognitive activity;
- stimulating the student to independent activity;
- development of adequate self-esteem;
- providing motivation, awareness;
- an active approach;
- focus on cooperation;
- step-by-step formation of knowledge, skills;
- using the life experience of students;
- orientation on feasibility,
- scientific knowledge;
- comfort of participants in the educational process [8, p.54].

Content, methods and techniques of work on the formation of economic knowledge, skills. Today, a junior high school student should know what money is, what the budget of the family and school comes from, what the price of goods is, what it depends on, how wealth is created and what its sources are.

And, of course, work in the field of economic education of younger schoolchildren requires the use of a variety of technologies when submitting material.

To activate students and maintain interest in the studied material, active teaching methods are used: business and role-playing games ("World of Professions", "Holiday Table", "Robinson", "Journey to Barter Island", "House Construction", "Unemployed and entrepreneurs" and others), computer and board games ("Life or Purse", "Monopoly", "Banker"), discussions on problematic economic topics, competition lessons ("The most economical hostess", "Conveyor", "Do you know the prices", "Knowledge Auction" and others), presentation lessons using the capabilities of computer technology. All this is informative and festive in nature. Positive emotional ocd

From the point of view of the cultural studies of education, culture is the sum of the spiritual achievements of mankind, the result and process of creativity, creative self-expression of people, the memory of mankind, the totality of sign systems, the totality of material and spiritual values, the inner achievements of the individual, attaching it to the sum of the achievements of society. The area of our research is the economic culture of primary school students. To determine its essence, it is necessary to clarify the content of the concept of "economic culture".

The analysis of philosophical, sociological and pedagogical literature on the problem of the formation of economic culture has shown the difference in approaches to the definition of the essence of the concept of "economic culture" with respect to its features, reflecting different directions of development of theoretical research in the field of general culture.

Culture, according to this approach, acts as a means of forming abilities, needs, feelings, that is, human social forces. In Uzbekistan, such an approach S.Bobokulov considers economic culture as "a set of intellectual, practical and emotional-value components that allow a person to self-actualize in economic activity and behavior, adapt and integrate into existing and projected socio-economic conditions, taking into account the moral and moral attitudes of society."

Nutfullo Khodjaev emphasizes that economic culture is the most important means of self-development, since a person with a formed economic culture not only creates, enriches and consumes cultural values, but also rises to a higher level of freedom in the process of his development [3, 87].

The "technological" approach, in contrast to the personal one, considers culture as a method (technology) and as a result of activity. This position is reflected in the designation of economic culture as organic (knowledge, conviction and creative practical activity, as well as the results of this activity, which are created by people during the development of society).

Some researchers in the definition of economic culture emphasize that it is one of the types of general culture and, having specific differences, carries in its content common generic features: knowledge, humanistic orientation of assimilation and development of knowledge, their application in practice.

In the light of modern trends, new approaches to the definition of economic culture have emerged. Scientists S. Bobokulov, M. Dzhumayev, H. Zhumashev, interpret economic culture as a system of values and motives for economic activity, respect for any form of ownership and commercial success as a great social achievement, the creation and development of a social environment for entrepreneurship [3, p. 92].

In our opinion, this definition of economic culture is interpreted taking into account modern socio-economic conditions and reflects the market, commercial side of public relations.

Thus, taking into account the above, we consider it possible to define economic culture as a qualitative characteristic of a person, showing the level of formation of economic knowledge, skills and practical economic activity, the development of economic thinking and consciousness, the degree of realization of economically significant personal qualities in the sphere of social production, distribution, exchange and consumption. Let's consider the influence and significance of the age characteristics of younger schoolchildren on the formation of the foundations of economic culture, bearing in mind that economic life is their natural and everyday environment.

Proceeding from this, economic education and upbringing should be aimed, in addition to familiarizing children with economic concepts and categories, at systematization, deepening and comprehension of their own life experience acquired by them in everyday life, the formation of an economic culture adequate in its level to the psychological capabilities of a younger student. Consequently, the educational process in a comprehensive school should provide for an individual approach and differentiation of students by age groups, taking into account the complexity of the tasks being solved. The need to take into account these features when it comes to economic education means the use of such organizational forms, methods and means that would meet the needs and capabilities of a given age [5, p.58]. By the time a child enters school, according to researchers, he has in his active vocabulary more than 25 economic concepts that are related to labor and its processes. These are objects and results of labor, individual and collective labor, marriage, products, materials, bonus, planning, salary, price, goods, etc.

They are familiar with words such as money, price, cost, etc. Operations with them are understandable for children: buy, sell, more expensive - cheaper, profitable - unprofitable, won - lost, changed, etc. According to our own observations, the volume of a child's economic vocabulary can be much larger and depends on many factors: place of residence (city, village), the level of prosperity in the family, the availability of self-employment, etc.

As a result of the joint activities of the family, vocational education institutions, additional structures of professional education, those participating in the beginning of school have an active interest in the phenomena of socio-economic reality. They are able to show economic thinking, a healthy interest in money, are ready to realize the connection "labor - money", the impossibility of

meeting all needs, recognize the facts of purchase and sale, get primary ideas about some professions related to the economic life of society (cashier, salesman, manager, accountant, etc.).

An important condition for the success of the implementation of economic education, as well as any other direction of the pedagogical process, is the timeliness of the implementation of pedagogical influence, the involvement of the child in activities aimed at achieving certain pedagogical goals. "You can't teach any subject too early, ... you can't teach any subject too late, there are always the best age periods for learning. The downward or upward bias from these optimal terms turns out to be equally disastrous" (11; 92).

The sensitive period for assigning any psychological role is primary school age. It is during this period that the child assumes a certain psychological orientation for the future ("leadership (organization)", "acquisitiveness", "responsibility", "individualism", "altruism", etc.), Depending on what ethical orientation the psychological image chosen by the child will have, later the type of his economic behavior will be determined(6; 7).

Elementary personal manifestations are also being formed: by the time they enter school, children already have a certain perseverance, can set themselves more distant goals and achieve them (although they often do not finish the job), make the first attempts to evaluate actions from the position of their social significance, they are characterized by the first manifestations of a sense of duty, responsibility. There is a great desire to engage in useful activities, its socio-economic motives are developing.

My own experience of observing objective real life is also sufficient and certainly contains familiarity with a significant number of economic concepts and phenomena. The possibilities of children, therefore, by the time they enter school are large enough to begin their systematic economic education and upbringing. As for the subjective psychological readiness of the child to study economic concepts, it depends on his individual characteristics, determined by the state of health, living conditions and activities of the child, the composition of the family, its level of security, family way of life, etc. When choosing forms and methods of economic education and education of younger schoolchildren, it is necessary to take into account the peculiarities of the development of cognitive processes at this age. So, younger schoolchildren are distinguished by sharpness and freshness of perception. A distinctive feature of perception at this age is its small differentiation.

Younger schoolchildren inaccurately and erroneously differentiate similar objects, concepts, for example, identify the concepts of "economy" and "economy". Children are characterized by a weakness of in-depth, organized and purposeful analysis in perception. Often they highlight random details that an adult will not pay attention to, while the essential and important are not perceived. Therefore, it is better to study similar or opposite economic concepts at the same time, showing children the essence of their similarities or differences(8-9).

It is known that the perception of students at the beginning of primary school age, firstly, increases dramatically, being supported by the practical activities of the child, and secondly, the most important catalyst for perception is emotionality. Therefore, when preparing children economically, it is necessary to use visual, vivid, lively information that is perceived better, more clearly, more emotionally than, for example, symbolic schemes and images, it is necessary to apply practical methods that activate the child's activity, various game forms, non-traditional tasks, which will allow the child to focus on the studied economic concepts. References to the child's own economic experience should be considered very productive.

The main feature of attention is the weakness of arbitrary attention. A younger student can force himself to work intently only if there is a close motivation (the prospects of getting a "five", earning the praise of the teacher, coping with the task best of all, etc.) Involuntary attention is much better developed at this age. Therefore, the most important condition for the organization of attention in the process of economic training is the visibility of training, the use of new, bright, catchy visual aids. Familiarity with such abstract concepts as "budget", "plan", "profit" and others requires extensive use of illustrations, drawings, posters. However, we must remember that younger students are very impressionable. Very vivid visual impressions can sometimes create such a focus of excitement in the cerebral cortex that as a result, any opportunity to understand the explanation will slow down.

Another important age-related feature of attention is its relatively small stability. Therefore, oral explanations of complex and abstract economic concepts should be alternated with practical work, contests, problem solving, etc. The variety of work stimulates the attention of schoolchildren and increases interest in economic knowledge.

The weakness of arbitrary attention and its instability dictate the need for the full use of games, especially role-playing games that model people's behavior and their relationships in various economic situations [6, p.81]. The analytical activity of a junior schoolboy, as is known, develops in the direction from visual-effective to abstract-mental analysis; from the analysis of an individual subject, phenomenon to the analysis of connections and relationships between objects and phenomena. The latter is a necessary prerequisite for students to understand the economic processes and phenomena of the surrounding life. In order for the child to understand the new economic concept, the teacher must create such conditions in the learning process that the child can relate this concept to the one already studied, include it in the systems.

Thus, the formation of the foundations of economic culture, as a qualitative characteristic of a person, showing the level of formation of economic knowledge, skills and practical economic activity, the development of economic thinking and consciousness, may well be realized at primary school age, as it meets all the necessary psychological and pedagogical parameters of this age.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 PD- No. 5847 "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030". // National database of legal documents, 09.10.2019, No. 06/19/5847/3887.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 No. PD-5847 "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030".
3. Bobokulov S. Profession - craftsman his collegial team took measures to form the II National Journal of education. 2003.#4, B.72-74.
4. Bobokulov S. Dzhumayev M. Highly specialized economics literacy formation of objective and subjective statistical data. II Uzluksiz journal of training. 2004.#5, B.35-39.
5. Djumayev M.I. The development of mathematical abilities in younger students. Science And Innovation International Scientific Journal Volume 2 Issue 1 January 2023 Uif-2022: 8.2 | Issn: 2181-3337 | Scientists.Uz/ 424-434

6. Djumayev M.I Formation of mathematical competence in future primary school teachers in the. Educational process science and innovation international scientific journal volume 2 issue 3 march 2023 uif-2022: 8.2 | issn: 2181-3337 | scientists.uz 165-173
7. Djumayev M.I The transformation of re english language's variants in contemporary Great Britain. Educational process science and innovation international scientific journal volume 2 Issue 4 April 2023 Uif-2022: 8.2 | Issn: 2181-3337 | Scientists.Uz 19-27
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7818607>
8. Djumaev M.I. (2023) Some Considerations of Teaching Mathematics Inuzbek Primary School. Journal of Mathematical & Computer Applications. SRC/JMCA-123. *J Mathe & Comp Appli*, 2023 Volume 2(2): 1-5 ISSN: 2754-6705
9. Dzhumaev M.I. Prospects for improving the teaching of mathematics at school, college and university of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Yamalo.Nanetsk Russia "PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION OF THE ARCTIC REGIONS" No. 1, MARCH, 2023. 3-6 st
10. Djumaev M.I. Some Considerations of Teaching Mathematics Inuzbek Primary School. Journal of Mathematical & Computer Applications. Received: March 28, 2023; Accepted: April 03, 2023, Published: April 22, 2023 ISSN: 2754-6705 1-5
11. Kozlova E.V. Psychological features of economic socialization of youth in modern conditions. -M., 2004. 292 p.
12. Maksakova V.I. Economic culture of personality. -M., 1989, 257 p